

Toxopathological effect of AFB1 on pregnant rats

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Abstract

The present study was carried on Twenty-one female virgin Wistar rats to evaluate toxopathological effects of AFB1 on pregnant female rats and their offspring at dose of 1mg/kg.

b. wt. from 6-15 days of gestation period. Pregnant dams revealed significant decrease in their body weight, gross enlargement of liver, liver showed necrosis, central vein was dilated and congested, kidney revealed interstitial hemorrhages, cast in their lumens, degeneration and necrosis, and lung revealed lymphocytic infiltrates in the interstitial tissue and the spleen revealed lymphoid depletion. Pathological lesions of fetu were dissociation of the hepatic cords, congestion of central vein and hepatic sinusoids, Kidney revealed degenerative changes in the renal tubules, thymus revealed lymphoid depletion.

Key words: AFB1, pregnant rats, hepatotoxicity, nephrotoxicity.

Introduction

Mycotoxins are secondary metabolites produced by different fungal species that can be found in many agricultural commodities and processed food (Bennett & Klich, 2003). Production of mycotoxins can occur in the field before harvest, postharvest, during storage, processing, and feeding under a wide range of climatic conditions. They are produced primarily by molds of the genera *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, and *Penicillium* (CAST, 1989). Mycotoxins implicated as chemical agents of acute or chronic diseases in animals and human (CAST, 2003). Acute effects of mycotoxin poisoning lead to the deterioration of the liver and kidney functions, allergic responses and immunosuppression, whereas chronic effects include mutagenicity, teratogenicity and carcinogenicity, it is also known to cause hepatic carcinoma in humans. (D'Mello & MacDonald, 1997; Pitt, 2000). Aflatoxins (AFs) are naturally- occurring mycotoxins, produced as secondary metabolites by the fungus *Aspergillus flavus*, *A.parasiticus*, and *A. nominus*; and are direct contaminants of cereals, grains, nuts and fruits (CAST, 2003). More than 5 billion people in developing countries worldwide are at risk of chronic exposure to naturally occurring aflatoxins (Williams et al., 2004). Fungal deterioration of stored seeds and

grains is a chronic problem in the Egyptian storage system because of the tropical hot and humid climate. Harvested grains are colonized by various species of *Aspergillus*, under such conditions leading to deterioration and mycotoxin production. *Aspergilli* are the most common fungal species that can produce mycotoxins in food and feedstuffs (Probst, Njapau, & Cotty, 2007; B. N. Reddy & Roghavender, 2007; K. R. N. Reddy, Reddy, & Muralidharan, 2009). Mycotoxins may cause public health problems and its ingestion during pregnancy may not be regarded entirely without risk to intrauterine life (Jonsyn, Maxwell, & Hendrickse, 1995; Yousef, Abdulrazzaq & Ahmed, 2002). Therefore, the present study aimed to: Investigate the different pathological effects of AFB1 on mothers. Investigate the different pathological effects of AFB1 on the fetu, before and after parturition.

Material and Methods

Experimental Animals

Sexually mature virgin female Wistar rats weighting 175-200 gm. with an average age 2.5-3 months were used for the present study. They were housed in cages in the animal House of Department of pathology, Faculty of veterinary medicine, Suez Canal University. They were maintained under standard environmental

condition (temperature of 20-25°C and 12-hour light dark cycle). The animals were acclimatized to lab. Conditions for one week before starting the experiment. They were fed on standard rodent pellets. Rats had free access to water and standard rat diet throughout the experiment.

Animal breeding

Mating was conducted by housing females & males in same cages at a ratio of one male with three females overnight. Vaginal smears for all females were examined and the presence of vaginal plug or sperm in the smear was considered as day zero of pregnancy.

Chemical substance:

Aflatoxin B1 was obtained from Sigma Chemical Ltd. (St. Louis, USA). For the preparation of the stock solutions, calculated amounts of AFB1 (10mg/ 10 ml corn oil) was added and heated gently to facilitate proper mixing of the toxins in the corn oil. The stock solutions were further diluted in corn oil to obtain the working solutions of 1mg/1ml for AFB1.

Experimental design

Twenty-one pregnant female rats were divided into 3 equal groups, seven animals in each group, treated orally from the sixth to 15 day of gestation period and sacrificed at 20th day of pregnancy as follow:

Group (I): Animals of this group served as control and received nothing all over the experimental period.

Group (II): Animals of this group served as control and intra gastrically administered the vehicle (corn oil) in the same quantity of the treatment.

Group (III): Animals of this group intra gastrically administered Aflatoxin B1 (AFB1) through gavage tube (1 mg/kg. wt). During test period, any clinical signs of poisoning were recorded.

Examination of mother and feti Morphological examination of pregnant dams and feti: The gradual increase in maternal body weight was considered as a sign for pregnancy. Any sudden decrease in the maternal body weight and/ or

presence of blood drops were considered as sign of abortion. The gestation period in rats was about 21 days. Body weight of Pregnant rats of both control and treated groups were recorded every day throughout the gestation period.

On 20th day of gestation, all pregnant dams of all groups (group I& II& III) were sacrificed. Maternal observations included number of corpora lutea, number of implantations, post-implantation loss, placental weight, number of live and dead feti, fetal crown to rump lengths, and fetal weights. Each fetus was carefully examined for gross anomalies. The feti from were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin, and examined for visceral anomalies.

Histological preparation for microscopical examination

Dams

All dams were sacrificed at the end of experimental period (20th day of pregnancy) tissue samples from liver, kidney, lung, spleen, intestine and brain were taken fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin. The specimens were processed and histological sections at 4-5µ were prepared and stained with haematoxylin & eosin, according to (Bancroft & Gamble, 2007).

Feti:

Feti from groups I, II & III at 20th day of pregnancy were sacrificed and fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for three days.

The skin of feti was incised in different thoracic and abdominal regions to allow rapid and perfect penetration of the fixative to the internal organs, as well, injection of

0.5 cm. of fixative in the peritoneal cavity. After the first 24 hours of fixation, the body was cut longitudinally into two parts, returned to the fixative to complete fixation and then washed under the running water for 10-24 hrs. Histological sections at 4-5µ were done, stained with H& E and safranin O according to (Bancroft & Gamble, 2007).

Statistical analysis:

SPSS (Version, 16) software package was used in the analysis. Data obtained were analyzed by Analysis of Variance (F- test). For Mean

separations, Duncan Multiple Range Test was used. For all statistical Methods, results considered significant at ($P \leq 0.05$).

Results

Maternal findings: Clinical signs:

No clinical signs or behavior alterations were observed in rats of control groups throughout the course of the experiment. Rats administered

AFB1 (1 mg/ kg b.wt.) showed signs of decreased activity, decreased response to external stimuli, lesser attraction toward feed and water, signs of dehydration characterized by dry rough skin tenting upon picking, polyuria, yellow colored diarrhea with loose consistency and daily decrease in the body weight.

Table (1): changes in maternal body weight during dosing period of pregnancy in all groups.

	Dosing	Group I	Group II	Group III & IV
Means of maternal body weights	1 (6 th day)	175	168	170
	2 (7 th day)	178	191	170
	3 (8 th day)	178	191	166
	4 (9 th day)	184	194	160
	5 (10 th day)	185	196	156
	6 (11 th day)	194	201	151
	7 (12 th day)	199	204	148
	8 (13 th day)	201	207	146
	9 (14 th day)	209	220	147
	10 (15 th day)	217	231	144
Total Mean \pm SE		192.00 ^a \pm 4.52	200.30 ^a \pm 5.43	155.00 ^b \pm 3.20

Within the row of total means, means that carrying different superscripts are highly significant (p value ≤ 0.01).

Table (2): Placental weight (gm.)

	Control	Corn oil	AFB1
	Mean \pm SE	Mean \pm SE	Mean \pm SE
Placental weight	0.52 ^a \pm 0.018	0.48 ^a \pm 0.014	0.42 ^b \pm 0.014

Within the same row, means carrying different superscripts are significant (p value ≤ 0.01).

Table (3): Fetal weight (gm.)

	control	Corn oil	AFB1
	Mean \pm SE	Mean \pm SE	Mean \pm SE
Pre parturition	2.13 ^b \pm 0.02	2.57 ^a \pm 0.06	1.10 ^c \pm 0.07
Post parturition	5.79 ^a \pm 0.14	5.97 ^a \pm 0.18	4.87 ^b \pm 0.12

Within the same row, means carrying different superscripts are significant (p value ≤ 0.01).

Table (4): Fetal crown to rump length (cm)

	Control	Corn oil	AFB1
	Mean \pm SE	Mean \pm SE	Mean \pm SE
Fetal crown to rump length	3.78 ^a \pm 0.088	3.22 ^b \pm 0.088	1.94 ^c \pm 0.15

Within the same row, means carrying different superscripts are significant (p Value ≤ 0.01).

Changes in the weight:

The body weight and body weight gain of control and treated rats (AFB1 1mg/ kg. b.wt.) at different days of gestation presented in tables "1". The treated groups had a significant decrease in the body weight gain as compared to control. AFB1 caused a significant reduction in

the weight of placenta of AFB1 treated groups compared to control and corn oil groups, as shown in Table "2". In addition, AFB1 caused a significant reduction in the weight of fetu from AFB1 treated group compared to control and corn oil groups, as shown in Table "3".

Gross pathology:

No gross morphological alterations were observed in rats of control groups. Rats administered AFB1 (1 mg/ kg. b.wt.) had shown enlargement in the size of liver, congestion and other pale yellow discoloration areas.

Histopathology Liver:

Rats of control groups did not show any histopathological alteration in liver tissue. In AFB1 groups, hepatocytes were swollen and exhibited cytoplasmic vacuoles. Some hepatocytes had pyknotic nuclei, foci of cellular necrosis in the parenchyma, disorganized hepatic cord pattern and the central vein was dilated and congested. Portal areas showed newly formed bile ducts "Fig. 1".

Kidneys:

Rats in control group did not show any histopathological alteration in the kidney tissue. In AFB1 group, there was interstitial hemorrhages and necrosis in some proximal and distal convoluted tubules. Degeneration and necrosis of distal convoluted tubules in these tubules there were renal casts "Fig. 2". Spleen: The main alterations observed in spleen from AFB1 treated group were lymphoid depletion in the white pulp and hemosiderosis in the red pulp "Fig. 3".

Fetal finding

The clinical findings: Mean fetal weights and crown to rump lengths significantly decreased in the AFB1 treated groups compared to controls. Table (3, 4).

Gross anomalies: There was a significant increase in the percent of gross anomalies in the fetuses of the AFB1 treated groups as compared with that of the control as wrinkling of skin, adactylia (absence of digits) and exophthalmia.

Histopathological finding:

The sections of the fetuses from the dams treated with 1.00 mg/kg of AFB1 revealed severe degenerative changes in various organs.

The liver was the most severely affected organ. The hepatocytes showed clumping and degeneration. The normal architecture of the hepatic parenchyma was distorted. As compared with controls, the megakaryocytes were depleted in number, they were enlarged with hazy cytoplasm, central vein, and hepatic sinusoids are congested and engorged with RBCs "Fig. 4".

Thymus had shown alterations characterized by lymphoid depletion and poor differentiation of epithelial cells and lymphoid components.

Figure 1: histopathological section of liver

A): histopathological section of liver from control adult female rat 1day post-partum (H & E stain, X400). **B):** histopathological section of liver of rat treated with aflatoxin B1 (1-day post-partum) showing dilated, congested central vein & focal necrotic area (H & E stain, X400).

Figure 2: histopathological section of kidney

(A): histopathological section of kidney of control adult female showing normal glomerulus and renal tubules (H&E stain, x400). (B): histopathological section of kidney of treated rat with AFB1 “1 mg / kg b.wt” showing degenerated tubules with congestion and hyperemia & presence of red hyaline cast in the renal tubules (H&E stain, x400).

Figure 3: histopathological section of spleen

(A): histopathological section of spleen of control adult female rat spleen showing normal splenic structure (white and red pulp) (H&E stain, X 400). (B): histopathological section of rat spleen from treated group with AFB1 “1 mg / kg. b.wt” showing lymphoid depletion in the white pulp (H&E stain, X 400).

Figure 4: histopathological section of the liver

(C): histopathological section of the liver of treated rat fetus with AFB1 at 20th days of pregnancy showing congestion and engorgement of the central vein and hepatic sinusoids with blood (H&E stain, x100). (D): high magnification of tissue at square of the figure C showing congestion and engorgement of the central vein and hepatic sinusoids with blood (H&E stain, x400).

Discussion

The present study was conducted to assess the toxopathological effects induced by AFB1 toxicities on pregnant albino female rats and their fetuses before and after parturition. Regarding the feed intake results, rats fed AFB1 at level of 1 mg/kg. B.wt. exhibited a significant decrease in feed intake and body weights compared to control groups. The reduced feed intake may indicate protein catabolism, indicated by the observed kidney injury and the ability of AFs to generate free radicals which may lead to DNA breakage, inhibition of protein biosynthesis and gluconeogenesis, lipid peroxidation, disruption of oxidative phosphorylation in mitochondria, inhibition of blood clotting and apoptosis (M. A. Abdel-Wahhab, Abdel-Azim, & El-Nekeety, 2008; Parhizkar, Mirhadi, & Allameh, 2002; Tessari, Oliveira, Cardoso, Ledoux, & Rottinghaus, 2006). Similar decrease in food consumption and body weight was reported in rats and mice fed AFB1 contaminated diet (M. A. Abdel-Wahhab & Aly, 2003; El-Nekeety et al., 2007; Madrigal-Santillan, Alvarez-Gonzalez, Marquez-Marquez, Velazquez-Guadarrama, & Madrigal-Bujaidar, 2007; Madrigal-Santillan, Madrigal-Bujaidar, Marquez-Marquez, & Reyes, 2006; Mayura et al., 1998; Saad & Abdel-Fattah, 2008). The reduction in body weight may be explained by the effect of mycotoxins on the balance between orexigenic and anorexigenic circuits that regulate the homeostatic loop of body weight regulation, leading to cachexia (Rastogi, Srivastava, & Rastogi, 2001). In this regard, (M. Abdel-Wahhab, Ahmed, & Hagazi, 2006) reported that rats treated with AFB1 showed a significant decrease in leptin; which and its receptor are the key players in the regulation of energy balance and body weight control which together act to influence the feeding response, causing weight loss (Yuan et al., 2004). In the present study, the observed pathological lesions in the liver of AFB1 treated rats were congested central veins, damaged bile ducts and massive vacuolar

degeneration with shrunken, pyknotic and abnormal nuclei. Kidney revealed interstitial hemorrhages and pyknotic nuclei of both proximal and distal convoluted tubules. Distal tubules had coagulated homogenous eosinophilic material (cast) in their lumens, with degeneration and necrosis of tubular epithelial cells. The histological changes observed in the liver and kidneys induced by Aflatoxin have been documented previously by (M. A. Abdel-Wahhab et al., 2007; Mayura et al., 1998). (M. A. Abdel-Wahhab, Nada, & Khalil, 2002; El-Nekeety et al., 2007; Gelderblom, Marasas, & Lebepe-Mazur, 2002) stated that AFB1 treatment induced a severe cytotoxicity and inhibition of hepatocytes cell proliferation (M. A. Abdel-Wahhab, Nada, Farag, Abbas, & Amra, 1998; M. A. Abdel-Wahhab et al., 2002; M. A. Abdel-Wahhab et al., 2007).

In this concern, treatment with AFB1 resulted in increased numbers of both apoptotic cell and mitoses in the periportal regions; the nuclei of these cells were enlarged; hyperchromatic and pleomorphic with a coarse chromatin pattern and their cytoplasm were distinctly large (megalocytosis). Same observation recorded by (Naaz et al., 2007; Balaji et al., 2009; Yener et al., 2009; El-Agamy, 2010). In this concern, treatment with AFB1 resulted in increased numbers of both apoptotic cell and mitoses in the periportal regions; the nuclei of these cells were enlarged; hyperchromatic and pleomorphic with a coarse chromatin pattern and their cytoplasm were distinctly large (megalocytosis). Same observation recorded by (Balaji, Suba, Rekha, & Deecaraman, 2009; El-Agamy, 2010; Naaz, Javed, & Abdin, 2007; Yener, Celik, Ilhan, & Bal, 2009). Kidneys of the AFB1 treated group showed moderate focal to diffuse necrosis in the renal tubules and swelling of renal tubular cells with occlusions of their lumens with local edematous changes in the kidneys of AFs-intoxicated rats. Histopathological lesions induced by AFs in liver and kidneys of rats in the present study were similar to those reported by other workers

(M. A. Abdel-Wahhab et al., 2007; Ezz El-Arab, Girgis, Hegazy, & Abd El-Khalek, 2006; Hussain, Zargham, Khan, Javed, & Rafique, 2009; Orsi et al., 2007; Saad & Abdel-Fattah, 2008). In the lymphoid or hematopoietic organ as spleen of rats treated with AFs lymphoid depletion in the white pulp and hemosiderosis in the red pulp were observed. This is supported by some authors who reported that exposure to aflatoxin B1 toxicity caused depletion of lymphoid cells in the lymph nodes (Prabu, Dwivedi, & Sharma, 2011). The main effect of these toxins is the inhibition of protein synthesis throughout binding with DNA and RNA perhaps as a result of interference with nitrogen metabolism produced immunosuppression and reduced antibody formation (Hassan, Hussain, El-Azzawy, & Saad, 1997; Hassan, Ragheb, Rahmy, & Nariman, 2004).

Conclusion

The present study and the overall data concluded that AFB1 at dose of 1 mg/ kg. Body weight, administered to pregnant rats during 6-15th days of gestation period is highly hepatotoxic, nephrotoxic & immunotoxic to both pregnant rats and their fetuses.

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